

Classifying Qubits Entanglements Using Partition's Logic

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March 2, 2021

Abstract

The aim of this paper is to show that how we can utilize *partition's logic* to classify some types of qubits entanglements in a simpler way rather than the methods which have been used. Indeed, the method which we will discuss here, is a motivation to considering partitions of a set as an ensemble of quantum states and studying qubits entanglements using *non-Boolean* underlying logic of partitions.

1 Introduction

There are two distinct known classes of entanglement of three qubits which are classified via algebraic methods and described by some geometrical tools, like *Fano plane, knots* and *links*. These three qubits entanglements have important role in quantum information theory and as well in black hole's studies. See [1], [2] and [3].

In present paper we will introduce a logical approach to classifying three qubits entanglements using the logic of partitions which is not a *Boolean logic*. We emphasize the role of *negation* as an important logical operator which has a pivotal role to magnifying the logical distinction of the mentioned two classes of entanglements. The general impacts of non-Boolean logical approach to quantum mechanics and its relation with *constructive mathematics* has been discussed in [4].

2 Partitions Theory

In this section the basic elements of *partitions theory* shall be discussed in detail. Although, the partitions are very familiar objects to mathematicians and people who study *dynamical systems*, but for quantum physicists are usually strangers, thus we added this section not merely to stabilize our notations but also to increase the self-sufficiency of this text. We start with the definition of a partition [8].

Definition 1 Let (X, Σ, μ) be a probability distribution space with σ -algebra Σ and measure μ . A finite collection of measurable sets, $\alpha = \{A_1, \dots, A_n\}$ when $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $A_i \in \Sigma$ for $i = 1, \dots, n$ is called a *finite partition* if the following properties are fulfilled:

- (a) $\forall i = 1, \dots, n; \mu(A_i) > 0$,
- (b) for $i \neq j; A_i \cap A_j = \emptyset$,
- (c) $\mu(X - (\bigcup_{i=1}^n A_i)) = 0$.

See figure 1.

Remark 1 Each element of a partition is called a **part** of partition.

Figure 1: Illustration of a set Ω with its two different partitions.

As well as what one will have seen in set theory, there are some operators between partitions. The first one would be the *joint operator* and the emerging partition will be *joint partition*. The definition of joint partition is as following.

Definition 2 Let $\alpha = \{A_1, \dots, A_n\}$ and $\beta = \{B_1, \dots, B_m\}$ are two partitions of the space X . We define the **joint partition** of these two partitions by:

$$\alpha \vee \beta := \{A_i \cap B_j | A_i \in \alpha, B_j \in \beta\}.$$

Definition 3 A finite partition X is a **refinement** of a finite partition Y whenever

$$\forall C \in X; \exists A \in Y : C \subset A.$$

In this case also we say X is “finer” than Y and we write $Y \preceq X$.

Remark 2 Notice that the relation \preceq might be very confusing in some sense. In different context the authors in Topos theory and probability theory maybe prefer to use converse relation. For our aims in this text, this relation with above definition is fine to have a well-define Heyting algebra. See [9] or [10].

As one may see in figure 1 a set Ω may have many different partitions. If we consider the set Ω itself, as a partition which has only one part (the whole set Ω), then both below partitions in the figure 1 are finer than it. Indeed, Ω is the less fine partition of itself or as we call, is the *coarsest partition* of Ω .

Another operator between partitions is the *meet operator* and is defined as follows.

Definition 4 Let X and Y be two partitions of a finite set Ω . **The Meet** of X and Y is denoted by $X \wedge Y$ and defined as the finest partition which is less fine than both X and Y .

To compute the meet of two partitions we will use the graph theoretic method which is introduced in [12].

Example 1 Consider $\Omega = \{1, \dots, 4\}$ and two of its partitions:

$$\begin{aligned} X_4 &= \{\{4\}, \{1, 2, 3\}\} \\ X_1 \vee X_2 &= \{\{1\}, \{2\}, \{3, 4\}\}. \end{aligned}$$

We associate a vertex with each element of Ω and draw a graph that has edges between each to vertices which are in a same part of at least one of partitions $X_4 = \{\{4\}, \{1, 2, 3\}\}$ or $X_1 \vee X_2 = \{\{1\}, \{2\}, \{3, 4\}\}$. So the graph is Figure 2. Now the parts of the meet partition are the connected components of above graph. So $(X_1 \vee X_2) \wedge X_4 = \{\{1, 2, 3, 4\}\} = \{\Omega\}$. Now consider partitions $X_1 \vee X_2 = \{\{1\}, \{2\}, \{3, 4\}\}$ and $X_2 \vee X_3 = \{\{2\}, \{3\}, \{1, 4\}\}$ and compute the meet partition for them. So we have: Figure 3

Thus the meet partition has two connected components $\{2\}$ and $\{1, 3, 4\}$. Hence we have:

$$(X_1 \vee X_2) \wedge (X_2 \vee X_3) = \{\{2\}, \{1, 3, 4\}\} = X_2$$

The next operator between two partitions is *implication operator*. This operator is defined as follows.

Definition 5 The Implication Partition $X \Rightarrow Y$ of two partitions X and Y of a finite set Ω is the partition whose parts are the connected components of the graph obtained by associating a vertex with each element of Ω and joining by an edge only those pairs of vertices which are in a same part of Y but not in a same part of X .

Example 2 Consider $\Omega = \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$ and these two partitions on it:

$$X_4 = \{\{4\}, \{1, 2, 3\}\} \text{ and } Y = \{\{1, 2\}, \{3, 4\}\}.$$

Figure 2: $(X_1 \vee X_2) \wedge X_4 = \{\{1, 2, 3, 4\}\} = \{\Omega\}$

Figure 3: $(X_1 \vee X_2) \wedge (X_2 \vee X_3) = \{\{2\}, \{1, 3, 4\}\} = X_2$

For computing $X_4 \Rightarrow Y$, following the above rules we draw the graph below and so we have the connected components: $\{1\}, \{2\}, \{3, 4\}$. Thus we have $(X_4 \Rightarrow Y) = \{\{1\}, \{2\}, \{3, 4\}\}$. See figure 4

Finally, similarly with set theory one may define a *negation operator* of a partition. The analogues of such a negation in set theory, as one will have seen before, is *complement of a set*. Primarily, we define a negation operator on partitions which give them a *Heyting algebra* structure, in progress, we will define another negation on this setting which will act on those partitions that playing the role of quantum states.

Definition 6 *The Negation or Pseudo-Complement of a partition X of a finite set Ω is denoted by $\neg X$ and defined as the partition $X \Rightarrow \{\Omega\}$.*

According to what we discussed above, one can easily see that the sextuple $(\pi(\Omega), \vee, \wedge, \Rightarrow, \neg, \preceq)$ is a distributive **Heyting Algebra** [10] whose bottom element is $\{\Omega\}$ and top element is $Atm(\Omega)$, where $(\pi(\Omega))$ is the set of all partitions on Ω . Thus, notice that the partition $\{\Omega\}$ is the coarsest partition and the partition $Atm(\Omega)$ is the finest partition on Ω .

Remark 3 *The order pair $(\pi(\Omega), \vee)$ is a monoid while $\{\Omega\}$ is its identity element. From another perspective $(\pi(\Omega))$ is a category. See [11]*

Figure 4: $X_4 \Rightarrow Y$

3 From Symbolic Superposition of Elements of a Set to Quantum Entanglements

Some physicists may argue that how and why we should consider partitions as ensemble of quantum states. We will show that, it can help us to classify some types of qubits entanglements, thus we will answer the question why and how at the same time. Nonetheless, we utilize a certain abstraction of the physical phenomena temporarily, to avoid such a phenomenological argument about the nature of quantum states till the moment that naturally one can see the heart of this correspondence. In addition, we will introduced a new quantum gate which helps us to pursue our aims in this paper.

Definition 7 Suppose $\Omega = \{\omega_1, \omega_2, \dots, \omega_n\}$ is a set, $n \geq 2$ and $(\pi(\Omega), \vee)$ is the monoid of all partitions on it. We define a map $\sigma : \Omega \times \Omega \rightarrow \pi(\Omega)$ such that for each $i \neq j$, $(\omega_i, \omega_j) \in \Omega \times \Omega$, $\sigma(\omega_i, \omega_j) = \Omega_{i,j}$ while ω_i and ω_j belong to a same part of $\Omega_{i,j}$ and $\Omega_{i,j}$ is the finest partition with this property. In addition, we assume that for $i = j$, $\sigma(\omega_i, \omega_i) = \text{Atm}(\Omega)$. Then we say $\Omega_{i,j}$ is the **symbolic superposition** of ω_i and ω_j . Also, We call the partitions $\Omega_{i,j}$'s, **symbolic quantum states**.

Example 3 Consider $\Omega = \{0, 1\}$. Then we have

$$\sigma(0, 1) = \Omega_{0,1} = \{\Omega\}$$

, while $\sigma(0, 0) = \sigma(1, 1) = \text{Atm}(\Omega) = \{\{0\}, \{1\}\}$. Thus, in this case symbolic superposition of 0 and 1 is the partition $\Omega_{0,1} = \{\Omega\}$. Notice that despite the fact that $\{\Omega\}$ is the coarsest partition on the set Ω , This is still the finest one such that 0 and 1 belong to a same part of it. In atomic partition 0 and 1 belong to different partitions.

Example 4 Suppose $\Omega = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$. Then we have:

$$\sigma(0, 1) = \Omega_{0,1} = \{\{0, 1\}, \{2\}, \{3\}\}.$$

Here, The partition $\Omega_{0,1}$ is the symbolic superposition of 0 and 1. Notice that the partition $\{\{0, 1\}, \{2, 3\}\}$ is not the symbolic superposition of 0 and 1, despite

the fact that 0 and 1 belong to the same part of it. The reason why is that clearly $\Omega_{0,1}$ is finer than this partition. For another example of symbolic superposition, here, the partition $\Omega_{1,3} = \{\{1,3\}, \{0\}, \{2\}\}$ is the symbolic superposition of 1 and 3.

Remark 4 Notice that $Atm(\Omega)$ never is not a symbolic superposition of any pairs of letters. Thus we say that atomic partition $Atm(\Omega)$ is **the classical configuration** of the set Ω .

It is clear that one can generalize the definition 7 to deal with symbolic superposition of more than two elements of a set Ω . This generalization is as following.

Definition 8 Suppose $\Omega = \{\omega_1, \omega_2, \dots, \omega_n\}$ is a set, $n \geq 2$ and $(\pi(\Omega), \vee)$ is the monoid of all partitions on it. We define a map $\sigma : \Omega^s \rightarrow \pi(\Omega)$ such that for each $(\omega_{i_1}, \omega_{i_2}, \dots, \omega_{i_s}) \in \Omega^s$, $(i_1 \neq i_2 \neq \dots \neq i_s)$, we have:

$$\sigma(\omega_{i_1}, \dots, \omega_{i_s}) = \Omega_{i_1, \dots, i_s}$$

while $\omega_{i_1}, \dots, \omega_{i_s}$ belong to a same part of Ω_{i_1, \dots, i_s} and Ω_{i_1, \dots, i_s} be the finest partition with this property. Then we say Ω_{i_1, \dots, i_s} is the **symbolic superposition** of $\omega_{i_1}, \omega_{i_2}, \dots, \omega_{i_s}$ or say Ω_{i_1, \dots, i_s} is a **symbolic quantum state**.

In the following, we will introduce the main notions of quantum information theory which are needed to study on entanglements of qubits. First, the formal notion of a *quantum bit* or *qubit* is introduced.

Definition 9 A **qubit** is a generic quantum state which is expressed as a superposition of two mutually orthogonal states $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$ as follows:

$$|\Psi\rangle = \alpha |0\rangle + \beta |1\rangle$$

Where α and β are complex numbers and $|\alpha|^2 + |\beta|^2 = 1$.

Here, we introduce *Hadamard gate* which has a pivotal role to creating a superposition. The formal definition of Hadamard gate is as following.

Definition 10 The **Hadamard gate** is defined as the following 2×2 matrix:

$$H = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & -1 \end{bmatrix}$$

One of the most surprising notions of quantum mechanics which is th main subject of our study in this text is *entanglement*. It is defined as following.

Definition 11 Suppose that the Hilbert space \mathcal{H} associated with a composite system be the tensor product of the Hilbert spaces \mathcal{H}_i associated with the system's components i . In the simplest case of a bipartite quantum system, we have

$$\mathcal{H} = \mathcal{H}_1 \otimes \mathcal{H}_2.$$

A state in \mathcal{H} is called an **entangled** state if it can not be written as a simple tensor product of a state $|\alpha\rangle_1$ which belongs to \mathcal{H}_1 and a state $|\beta\rangle_2$ which belongs to \mathcal{H}_2 . In contrast, if we can write

$$|\psi\rangle = |\alpha\rangle_1 \otimes |\beta\rangle_2$$

we say the state ψ is **separable**. See [13] and [14].

Another important quantum gate in quantum information theory and our study about qubits entanglements is *CNOT gate*. Here, we introduce this gate.

Definition 12 Let $x, y \in \{0, 1\}$ and $|x\rangle, |y\rangle$ be two quantum states. We denote the **Controlled-Not gate** with **CNOT** and define as follows:

$$\mathbf{CNOT}(|x\rangle |y\rangle) = |x\rangle |x \oplus y\rangle,$$

Where \oplus means addition on modulo 2. See [14].

Controlled-Not is a two-qubits gates, rather than Hadamard gate which is single qubit case. The first qubit in C-NOT gate acts like a *control qubit* and the second qubit acts as a *target qubit*. If the control qubit be in the state $|1\rangle$ then C-NOT flips the target qubit, else does not anything on target qubit. See [14]

In this text, we are going to study *bipartite entanglements* and *tripartite entanglements of three qubits*, hence we need to utilize a three-qubit gate. There is a known gate that is called *Toffoli gate* and we will introduce it soon. In our viewpoint, despite of universality of Toffoli gate, as a gate which is enough for computation(See [14]), this gate is not the best option to study entanglements of three qubits. Universality is important for computational aspects, certainly, but to classifying entanglements as we will show later, Toffoli gate is not enable to carry out all the different features of distinguished types of entanglements. Thus, instead of trying to hold universality, which in this context, is related to a Boolean underlying logic of computation in a *Turing machine*¹, we want to introduce a gate which is useful to study trinary relations and specially, *the trinary relations* which we think that they are not reducible to composition of binary relations and we claim that using this suggested gate we can figure out the fundamental differences of some classes of entanglement.

At first we will see the definition of Toffoli gate and then we will introduce our suggested gate which we call it, *Trinity gate*.

Definition 13 Let $x, y \in \{0, 1\}$ and $|x\rangle, |y\rangle, |z\rangle$ be three quantum states. We denote the **Toffoli gate** with **Toff** and define as follows:

$$\mathbf{Toff}(|x\rangle |y\rangle |z\rangle) = |x\rangle |y\rangle |z \oplus xy\rangle$$

. Where \oplus means addition on modulo 2. See [14]

¹Indeed, since the underlying logic of the probability theory which is used to define probabilistic Turing machine is a Boolean logic too, the mentioned universality in the text, is also related to probabilistic Turing machine.

In this text we do not study computational aspects of the gate that we will introduce. Indeed, the study of universality or locality of this gate in a more general meaning of computation(in compare to computation via *binary arithmetic*) is the case of future studies.

Remark 5 In this text, always \oplus means addition on modulo 2.

Definition 14 Let $x, y \in \{0, 1\}$ and $|x\rangle, |y\rangle, |z\rangle$ be three quantum states. We denote the **Trinity gate** with ∇ and define as follows:

$$\nabla(|x\rangle|y\rangle|z\rangle) = |x\rangle|x \oplus y\rangle|z \oplus (x \oplus y)\rangle.$$

Notice that, despite of CNOT and Toff gates which have just one target qubit, Trinity gate has two target qubits, maybe in a mainstream meaning of computation, this feature will be quiet

Now, we are going to study entanglements of three qubits using our symbolic superposition notion and Trinity gate. To pursue this aim firstly we pick up a composite system of three qubits. Indeed, we have three two-state systems each with Hilbert space \mathbb{C}^2 . The Hilbert space of the total system is:

$$\mathcal{H} = \mathbb{C}^2 \otimes \mathbb{C}^2 \otimes \mathbb{C}^2.$$

See [3]. Three qubits can be entangled in two inequivalent ways, the unnormalized representatives of these classes are the so-called **Greenberger–Horne–Zeilinger state (GHZ state)** and **W state** and are defined as following.

$$|GHZ\rangle = \frac{|000\rangle + |111\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$$

and

$$|W\rangle = \frac{|001\rangle + |010\rangle + |100\rangle}{\sqrt{3}}.$$

See [3] Indeed, physicist using the notion of *Cayley's hyper-determinant* classified three qubits entanglement in these two above classes.

A generic three-qubit state can be represented as

$$|\psi\rangle = \sum_{ABC=0,1} \psi_{ABC} |ABC\rangle, \quad |ABC\rangle = |A\rangle \otimes |B\rangle \otimes |C\rangle \in \mathcal{H}_A \otimes \mathcal{H}_B \otimes \mathcal{H}_C$$

Under *SLOCC* transformations (*Stochastic Local Operation Classical Communication*) (see [3]) our state transforms as a (2,2,2) namely:

$$|\psi\rangle \mapsto (\mathcal{A} \otimes \mathcal{B} \otimes \mathcal{C}) |\psi\rangle, \quad \psi_{ABC} \mapsto \mathcal{A}'_A \mathcal{B}'_B \mathcal{C}'_C \psi_{A'B'C'}, \quad \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B}, \mathcal{C} \in \text{GL}(2, \mathbb{C}).$$

Now one can define **Cayley's hyper-determinant** as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} D(\psi) = & [\psi_0\psi_7 - \psi_1\psi_6 - \psi_2\psi_5 - \psi_3\psi_4]^2 - 4[(\psi_1\psi_6)(\psi_2\psi_5) \\ & + (\psi_2\psi_5)(\psi_3\psi_4) + (\psi_3\psi_4)(\psi_1\psi_6)] \\ & + 4\psi_1\psi_2\psi_4\psi_7 + 4\psi_0\psi_3\psi_5\psi_6, \end{aligned}$$

where $(\psi_0, \psi_1, \dots, \psi_7) \equiv (\psi_{000}, \psi_{001}, \dots, \psi_{111})$ [3].

The $|GHZ\rangle$ -class is characterised by $D(|GHZ\rangle) \neq 0$ while $D(|W\rangle) = 0$. [3] Cayley's hyperdeterminant is a really nice tool to classifying the entanglements of three qubits, but one can easily see that how much is difficult to define and calculated this notion for entanglements of four or more qubits. In the following we reclassify these two class of entanglements of three qubit just by using partition logic and Trinity gate.

3.1 GHZ State

Initially, we write down the symbolic superposition(See defition 8) of the $|000\rangle$ and $|111\rangle$ as follows.

$$\Omega_{|000\rangle,|111\rangle} = \{\{|000\rangle, |111\rangle\}, \{\{|001\rangle\}, \{|100\rangle\}, \{|011\rangle\}, \{|010\rangle\}, \{|101\rangle\}, \{|110\rangle\}\}.$$

Indeed, we assigned $\Omega_{|000\rangle,|111\rangle}$ to $|GHZ\rangle$. Thus, since now, for the associated symbolic quantum state of GHZ state we write $\Omega_{|GHZ\rangle}$. Notice that, this partition is the finest partition which has $|000\rangle$ and $|111\rangle$ in the same part.

Now we compute the $\nabla(|GHZ\rangle)$. We have: $\nabla(|GHZ\rangle) = \frac{|000\rangle + |101\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$

Then, we send this new state again to the Trinity gate. Hence we have:

$$\nabla(\nabla(|GHZ\rangle)) = \frac{|000\rangle + |110\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \neq |GHZ\rangle.$$

This is our first interesting observation. Despite of the gate Toff, the Trinity gate does not obey the Boolean logical rule of the negation operator which says for a logical statement like q :

$$\neg(\neg(q)) \equiv q.$$

It means that, if we wish to construct a non-Boolean logical negation operator then the Trinity gate is a good option. Let us compute the Toff and see that it our claim about the difference between Toff gate and Trinity gate is correct.

We have: $\mathbf{Toff}(|GHZ\rangle) = \frac{|000\rangle + |110\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$, Hence:

$$\mathbf{Toff}(\mathbf{Toff}(|GHZ\rangle)) = \frac{|000\rangle + |111\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} = |GHZ\rangle.$$

Proposition 1 Suppose $\Omega = \{|ijk\rangle | i, j, k \in \{0, 1\}\}$ be the set of all eight possible quantum states of a three qubit system and $(\pi(\Omega), \vee)$ be the monoid of all symbolic quantum states of Ω . Then with respect to Heyting algebra $(\pi(\Omega), \vee, \wedge, \Rightarrow, \neg, \preceq)$ we have following for $\Omega_{|GHZ\rangle}$:

1. $(\Omega_{\nabla(|GHZ\rangle)} \Rightarrow \Omega_{|GHZ\rangle}) \equiv \Omega_{|GHZ\rangle}$.
2. $(\Omega_{\nabla(\nabla(|GHZ\rangle))} \Rightarrow \Omega_{|GHZ\rangle}) \equiv \Omega_{|GHZ\rangle}$.

Proof: In order to prove the both cases, we use our recent calculations in this subsection that say $\nabla(|GHZ\rangle) = \frac{|000\rangle + |101\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$ and $\nabla(\nabla(|GHZ\rangle)) = \frac{|000\rangle + |110\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$.

Thus we have: $\Omega_{\nabla(|GHZ\rangle)} = \Omega_{|000\rangle,|101\rangle}$ and $\Omega_{\nabla(\nabla(|GHZ\rangle))} = \Omega_{|000\rangle,|110\rangle}$. Now, using the graph-theoretical method which is introduced in [12] we compute the implications operators in both case and we finish the proof. \square

3.2 W State

Similarly with subsection 3.1, firstly, we write down the associated symbolic superposition of W state as follows.

$$\Omega_{|W\rangle} = \{|001\rangle, |010\rangle, |100\rangle, |011\rangle, |101\rangle, |110\rangle, |000\rangle, |111\rangle\}.$$

Now we compute the $\nabla(|W\rangle)$. We have $\nabla(|W\rangle) = \frac{|001\rangle + |011\rangle + |111\rangle}{\sqrt{3}}$.

Then we have:

$$\nabla(\nabla(|W\rangle)) = \frac{|001\rangle + |010\rangle + |101\rangle}{\sqrt{3}} \neq |W\rangle.$$

One can easily see that W state is invariant under $Toff$ gate. Till now, there is no logical difference between GHZ state and W state. Indeed both showing a non-Boolean feature of $\neg(\neg(q)) \equiv q$, regarding ∇ as a negation operator. The difference of these two entangled states, in our logical context, is related to second part of following proposition.

Proposition 2 *Suppose $\Omega = \{|ijk\rangle | i, j, k \in \{0, 1\}\}$ be the set of all eight possible quantum states of a three qubit system and $(\pi(\Omega), \vee)$ be the monoid of all symbolic quantum states of Ω . Then with respect to Heyting algebra $(\pi(\Omega), \vee, \wedge, \Rightarrow, \neg, \preceq)$ we have following for $\Omega_{|W\rangle}$:*

1. $(\Omega_{\nabla(|W\rangle)} \Rightarrow \Omega_{|W\rangle}) \equiv \Omega_{|W\rangle}$.
2. $(\Omega_{\nabla(\nabla(|W\rangle))} \Rightarrow \Omega_{|W\rangle}) \not\equiv \Omega_{|W\rangle}$.

Proof: Similarly with proposition 1, the proof is based on utilizing the graph-theoretic method which we have taken from [12] and explained in the section 2. The implication partition $(\Omega_{\nabla(|W\rangle)} \Rightarrow \Omega_{|W\rangle})$ will be the connected components of the graph which has only those edges of $\Omega_{|W\rangle}$ which do not exist in $\Omega_{\nabla(|W\rangle)}$. In this case, since $\Omega_{|W\rangle}$ and $\Omega_{\nabla(|W\rangle)}$ have no edges in common thus the partition is equal to $\Omega_{|W\rangle}$ (no edge is cancelled.) and the first statement is proved. For the second statement, note that $\{|001\rangle, |010\rangle\}$ can not be an edge in implication partition, because it is a common edge of $\Omega_{|W\rangle}$ and $\Omega_{\nabla(\nabla(|W\rangle))}$. Hence we have the non-equivalency of the second statement and proof is completed. \square

4 Conclusion and Further Discussions

There are some important technical issues which should be mentioned before conclusion. The operator ∇ , Trinity, which we introduced for the first time in this work, is not an alternative negation for the negation which is inside of the partition's logic $(\pi(\Omega), \vee, \wedge, \Rightarrow, \neg, \preceq)$. Indeed, Trinity regarding as a negation is defined on the common Boolean logic of information. It means that, Trinity is an operator on three qubits system. It just acts on qubits and not on the

partitions. Thus, actually, we generate some new quantum states using Trinity gate then some new symbolic superpositions came up consequently. Then we saw that this new symbolic superpositions, which are some partitions on the other hand, showed non-Boolean features.

Now, let us discuss what we conclude from the propositions 1 and 2 our discussion.

- Putting forward a merely logic-based discussion, specifically, utilizing partition's logic and Trinity gate, we classified two different classes of entanglements of three qubits. The representative of these two classes are GHZ state and W state.
- We saw that in a logical sense, W state is a more robust entanglement. More explicitly, However, GHZ and W both are not invariant under double acting of Trinity gate, regarding as negation operator, W has shown stronger non-Boolean behaviours in compare to GHZ . Roughly speaking, the proposition 1 says that, however $\nabla(\nabla(|GHZ\rangle)) \neq |GHZ\rangle$, still its associated symbolic superposition implies $\Omega_{|GHZ\rangle}$, while the proposition 2 says that is not the case for W state.
- Since, Heyting algebra is the internal logic of a *elementary topos* and conversely, an elementary topos can emerge in a *categorification process*(see [7]), our discussion in this paper may guide us to think about *constructive mathematics* and topos theory as an alternative foundation of modern physics. I addressed this point, in my previous paper, and discussed it from other aspects in that paper. See [4].

There are many directions to further researches. One of the main question is that what other types of non Boolean logical features may exist in quantum entanglements. Naturally, one may try to investigate a similar classification for four qubits systems and so on.

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